

THE STUDY OF PSYCHOLINGUISTICS IN THE FIELD OF LINGUISTICS

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Abstract. How does mind generates a thought and how is it prepared for speaking process? These are learnt in psycholinguistics. This paper is an attempt to learn more about the challenging but fascinating field of psycholinguistics and its interdisciplinary features in language acquisition process and comprehending language. And it is discussed the origin of the subject, its development and problems.

Key words: linguistics, psychology, psycholinguistics, actual problems of psycholinguistics

It is obvious that communication is considered as an important part of daily life. Language has been together with the humanity for ages. Language is the means by which we convey meaning or messages to one another. Beyond using linguists to teach grammar, reading, and foreign languages, studies of language and mind in psychology and education from the USA, Europe may significantly advance our understanding of how language is made and acquired.

In the following pages, linguistics and psycholinguistics will be defined, and the process of language acquisition will be briefly covered. Psycholinguistic elements at play, which serve as a foundation for teaching language and cognition. During my studies in this field, I have discovered a lot of information about this field. Many teachers, speech pathologists, and other educators are encountering the linguistic revolution.

What is linguistics? It is not a new phenomenon, but an old and respected scholarly field. The branch of linguistics evolved in the twentieth century. The linguist, whom we are concerned with, is not just the linguist who speaks and teaches many foreign languages, but he or she is the language scientist who investigates how language functions and forms. 'Linguistics is commonly defined as the 'science of languages' or 'the scientific study of language'¹. Linguistics, for the whole, is a big umbrella term that defines and learns the language itself universally.

As for psychology, it is a scientific field that studies human emotions, preferences, interests, needs, abilities, and capabilities. It is also considered as the science of mental state. Scientifically, 'Psychology was defined as 'the science of consciousness. Langacker (1973) in his book entitled *Language and Its Structure* states that Psycholinguistics is the study of language acquisition and language behavior, as well as the psychological mechanism responsible for them². Furthermore, the linguistic skills are also formulated in the mind. So the language and psychology are well interrelated with each other. Through verbal and nonverbal communication, people build psychological relationships with one another. They utilize both language and non-linguistic communication methods to engage with one another. The sciences of psychology and linguistics both attempt to explain how the object of existence and its name are interconnected in the human mind as they have similar properties in diverse discourses.

¹ Gordon & Ladefoged, 2001

² Langacker, Roland W.1973. *Language and Its Structure*.New York

Psychology and linguistics formed an interdisciplinary subject in linguistic field: psycholinguistics. It blends psychological and linguistic methods and theories. It seeks to assess the psychological reality and foundations of linguistic norms and processes. It also aims to connect word and phrase processing to deeper expressive processes such as message formulation and interpretation. It occupies into the fields of general linguistics, discourse analyses, applied languages and foreign language teaching. Psycholinguistics deals with the processes in formulating a thought and preparing it into the speaking.

The term psycholinguistics was first used in 1936 by Jaco Robert Kantor in his book *An Objective Psychology of Grammar*. Then it was used by his Indiana University team. However, it wasn't until 1946 that his student Nicholas Henry Pronko's article "Language and psycholinguistics: a review" made it widely used. It was initially utilized in the title of Charles E. Osgood and Thomas A. Sebeok's 1954 book *Psycholinguistics: A survey of theory and research difficulties*, as well as in discussions of a multidisciplinary science "that could be coherent"³.

Psycholinguistics studies how people learn, process, and utilize language by looking at how language is learned and processed in the brain. Its important, major concerns are :

1. Language Acquisition

What cognitive processes are involved in learning a first and second language, and how do children acquire language?

2. Language Production

What cognitive processes go into organizing, preparing, and producing spoken and written language, and how do humans produce language?

3. Language Comprehension

What cognitive processes are involved in deciphering spoken and written language, and how do we assimilate language?

4. Language Processing

What neurological processes are involved in language processing, and how does the brain process language?

5. Bilingualism

What are the cognitive and neural effects of learning and using more than one language?

6. Language Disorders

What are the cognitive and neural bases of language disorders, such as aphasia, dyslexia, and specific language impairment?

It is known that psycholinguistics has undergone enough alterations and issues although it has been newly introduced to the academic field as an independent discipline. Psycholinguistic problems refer to difficulties or challenges that individuals may face in language processing, comprehension, production, or acquisition due to various psychological factors. These problems can affect different aspects of language, including phonology (sounds), morphology (word structure), syntax (grammar), semantics (meaning), and pragmatics (language use in social contexts). Some common psycholinguistic problems include:

1. *Aphasia*: Aphasia is a language disorder that affects an individual's ability to understand or produce language due to brain damage, typically resulting from strokes or other neurological

³ Dr K. Balamurugan & Dr S. Thirunavukkarasu [‘Introduction to Psycholinguistics—A Review’](#)

conditions. People with aphasia may struggle with word retrieval, sentence formation, or understanding spoken or written language.

2. *Dyslexia*: Dyslexia is a learning disorder that primarily affects reading and spelling skills. People with dyslexia may have difficulties with letter recognition, phoneme awareness, and decoding words accurately. It can result in slow and inaccurate reading, writing, and comprehension.

3. *Specific Language Impairment (SLI)*: SLI is a developmental disorder that affects children's language ability without any obvious cause or other underlying conditions. Children with SLI may have difficulties with vocabulary development, grammar, sentence structure, and understanding complex language.

4. *Language processing difficulties*: Some individuals may have difficulties processing and comprehending language efficiently. This can involve difficulties with parsing sentences, understanding ambiguous or complex expressions, or following verbal instructions.

5. *Pragmatic language difficulties*: Pragmatic language difficulties refer to challenges in using language appropriately in social contexts. It may involve difficulties understanding or using non-literal language (such as sarcasm or irony), turn-taking in conversation, interpreting social cues, or adjusting language to different situations.

6. *Speech disorders*: Speech disorders, such as stuttering (disruptions in fluent speech) or articulation disorders (difficulties pronouncing sounds), can also be considered psycholinguistic problems as they affect the production and perception of language.

Psycholinguistic problems can have a significant impact on individuals' communication, academic performance, and social interactions. Treatment and intervention options vary depending on the specific problem and its underlying causes. Speech and language therapy, educational support, and specialized interventions can help individuals overcome or manage these challenges, improve their language skills, and enhance their overall communication abilities.

In conclusion, psycholinguistics is a field of study that explores the psychological processes involved in language comprehension, production, acquisition, and use. It examines how the human mind processes, stores, and retrieves linguistic information, as well as how various psychological factors can impact language abilities. Psycholinguistics helps us understand the complex and intricate relationship between language and cognition by investigating the cognitive processes and neural mechanisms that underlie language processing. It provides insights into the development of language skills, the impact of language disorders, and the influence of individual differences on language abilities.

By studying psycholinguistic problems, researchers and practitioners can devise effective interventions and strategies to support individuals with language difficulties. This field is crucial for improving our understanding of language comprehension and production, fostering effective communication, and facilitating language learning in various contexts.

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